

**TO SERVE, PROTECT, AND TRANSFORM: A JOURNEY WITH A
POLICE-EVANGELIST TOWARDS THE MORAL RECOVERY
AMONG OFFENDERS**

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To Serve, Protect, and Transform: A Journey with a Police-Evangelist towards the Moral Recovery among Offenders

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Abstract

This research disclosed the narrative of a police evangelist facilitating the moral recovery among offenders. Researchers utilized a qualitative single-case study design, employing one police officer who conducts spiritual services inside jail facilities chosen through a purposive sampling technique. This study aimed to motivational factors, experiences, and insights of the police-evangelist in journeying towards moral recovery among offenders. Researchers gathered the data through an in-depth interview and analyzed the data using thematic analysis to create themes and core ideas. Three emerging themes were created on the motivational factors of the police evangelist: driven by faith and compassion, responding to the call, and PDL's eagerness to be taught. Four themes emerged from the experiences of the police evangelist: conduct of spiritual services, getting support, joy in changing one's life, happiness and fulfillment, and dealing with PDL's different emotions. Three emerging themes were found in the insights of the police evangelist: volunteerism in sharing God's words, God's words change lives, and doing what you learned. This study substantiates the Social Learning Theory. Practical implications for the police officers, police stations, jail facilities, religious groups, and local government units were presented.

Keywords: *police evangelist, moral recovery, offenders, PDLs, single-case study*

Introduction

Prisoners experience emotional and psychological strains during their incarceration, as indicated by their feelings of anger, vengeance, depression, and loss of self-worth (Jang et al., 2021). Despite conflicting with the law, they deserve to be treated with value and dignity and assisted throughout their recovery and rehabilitation (United Nations, 2023).

Connectedly, apart from their roles as law enforcers, criminologists, and responders, police officers also have a significant role in achieving moral recovery among offenders. In fact, correctional officers understand that faith-based activities in prisons provide moral, emotional, and social support among offenders (Johnson, 2021).

So, they usually conduct religious interventions and advocate spiritual growth, religiosity, and forgiveness to reinforce the positive experiences of the prisoners (Gueta et al., 2022; Jang et al., 2022). The spiritual interventions spearheaded by the police officers most likely diminish the negative emotions of offenders and enhance their sense of meaning and purpose in life (Jang et al., 2021).

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to understand the narrative of a single-case police evangelist in facilitating moral recovery among offenders. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What motivational factors influence the police evangelist case to promote moral recovery among offenders?
2. What are the experiences of the police evangelist case in his journey towards moral recovery among offenders?
3. What are the insights of the police evangelist case about the jobs of police officers towards moral recovery among offenders?

Literature Review

Various studies have discussed the impact of the police's initiative to employ spiritual programs inside correctional facilities on the rehabilitation of offenders. For instance, correctional officers in the United States cooperate with faith-based or spiritually-led programs to provide spiritual services to prisoners and help them return to their communities with a more positive outlook (Roman & Roman, 2019). Relatedly, a study in New Zealand found that the officers purposefully conduct spiritual and religious programs inside jails with the help of chaplains, resulting in a lower likelihood and rate of reconviction among sexual offenders (Stansfield, 2020). In South Africa, the officers also help the offenders augment their perceived forgiveness of God, gratitude to God, and perceived positive impact of the Bible through spiritual interventions, like praise and worship, preaching, and Bible study (Jang, 2022).

The police in the Philippines police are driven to provide profound rehabilitation practices to the inmates in fulfillment of their duty to reinforce peace and order in the community. Thus, they strengthen their coordination with non-governmental organizations, specifically religious groups like CARITAS Charity, which gives spiritual messages and programs whenever they visit correctional facilities (Caparas, 2020). Similarly, in Ilocos, police officers observed a significant level of distress and anxiety among prisoners, so they conducted therapeutic intervention programs focusing on the offenders' religiosity and spirituality. This initiative built a positive and meaningful personal framework among offenders (Dioses, 2019).

The concepts and claims mentioned in the preceding paragraphs are anchored on the Social Learning Theory by Albert Bandura (1997),

who argued that learning occurs within a social context. People learn from observing the behaviors of a model and the outcomes of those behaviors (Astray-Caneda et al., 2011). In addition to Social Learning, Bandura's Theory of Modeling, or "Observational Learning," states that humans can control their behaviors through self-observation, self-judgment, and self-response (Bandura, 1991). Various authors (Astray et al., 2011; Gottfredson & Hirschi, 2019; Becker, 2021) use the concept of Social Learning Theory in criminological research, specifically in criminal engagement and prisoner rehabilitation. Relatively, the police officers and religious leaders act as models and are observed by the offenders. After the offenders observe the model's behavior, they will judge whether or not the effects of that behavior are beneficial. Then, they will choose whether to adopt the observed behaviors within themselves.

The importance of this study is anchored in the need to explore the experiences of an evangelist police officer in facilitating moral recovery among offenders. This unique perspective has not been well-explored in the research literature. This study contributed to our understanding of the role of religion and spirituality in rehabilitating offenders, a topic of growing interest as more and more correctional institutions offers faith-based programs (Hallett et al., 2019). This study also helped identify best practices for implementing moral recovery programs in correctional settings, which can be used to improve the effectiveness of these programs and help more offenders achieve successful rehabilitation (Castelino, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative single-case study approach as a research design. Such an approach in qualitative research was appropriate for this study since it aimed to identify the motivation, experiences, and insights of the single-case police evangelist who provides spiritual activities to the offenders. In a single-case study design, the researcher only studies one case representing a critical, unique, revelatory, or exploratory phenomenon (Yin, 2004; Ridder, 2017). Single-case study research scientifically investigates a real-life phenomenon in depth and within its environmental context. Such a case can be an individual, a group, an organization, an event, a problem, or an anomaly (Burawoy, 2009; Stake, 2005; Yin, 2014; Ridder, 2017).

In addition, the method of collecting data for case studies is through lengthy interviews to understand and interpret a participant's perception of the meaning of an event or case (Williams, 2016). Creswell (2008) further suggested that the procedural format is writing the research questions that explore the meaning of the experience, conducting the interviews, analyzing the data to find the clusters of meanings, and ending with a report that furthers the readers' understanding of the essential structure of the experience. The study collects data that identifies common themes in people's perceptions of their experiences.

Participants

This study employed only one participant to represent the single case. The inclusion criteria for selecting the participants are listed below. First, he must be a police officer who has rendered law enforcement services for at least five years. Second, he must be a baptized Christian for at least five years. Third, he must be personally included in the moral recovery program for offenders. Fourth, he must conduct spiritual interventions for the prisoners, such as preaching, praise, and worship. The participant who fulfills the criteria is deemed appropriate to sample in this study because he can reveal the motivation, experiences, and insights of a police evangelist regarding the moral recovery of offenders.

Additionally, a purposive sampling technique is used to choose the sole participant in the present case. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method wherein the sample is selected based on population characteristics and the study's objective. Purposive sampling is judgmental, selective, or subjective (Crossman, 2018). In qualitative research, the sample size is usually tiny primarily because phenomena only need to appear once to be part of the analytical map (Ritchie et al., 2013). It is typical to study a few individuals or a few cases. In-depth interview is often considered as a form of conversation. (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

Instruments

In case studies, the research questions drive the data to be collected. From the research questions, the researchers determined the kinds of questions to be asked in the interview. Therefore, in this study, the researchers used semi-structured interview questions during the in-depth interview (IDI) to identify the motivation, experiences, and insights of the sole participant in this case as he journeys toward moral recovery among offenders. The in-depth interview was loosely structured, allowing researchers and participants to discuss further ideas about their own experiences if needed (Boyce & Neale, 2006).

The data-gathering method is an interview in which participant statements are collected. Furthermore, the participant should give more profound insights and detailed statements as he answers semi-structured interview questions during the in-depth interview (IDI). Additionally, the researchers used a recording app on their mobile phones to obtain precise and accurate information. Transcription and analysis of these data recordings were performed after the interview. A series of validated interview guide questions were also used to facilitate transcription. Lastly, a copy of the interview transcripts was presented to the interviewee for verification.

Procedure

In collecting data, the researchers endorsed a proposal to the Research and Publication Center of UM Bansalan College. Then, they

asked permission from the school director to conduct this study. Further, a permission letter was sent to the police-evangelist participant to inform him about this research. Upon approval, the researchers started to gather data from the participants through an in-depth interview.

During the actual data collection, the participant was oriented about the conduct of the study, its significance, its purpose, and its objectives. He was asked to sign the Informed Consent Form stating their voluntary participation in the study. As a result, the participant was assured of their rights to confidentiality and privacy and that the data collected was used solely for the study. There was no misleading or potential harm during the interview; otherwise, the participants had the right to withdraw their participation.

The interview used interview guide questions, which were checked and validated by experts. The questions in the in-depth interview guide were explained thoroughly by the researchers. An audio recorder was used to record the conversation. Note-taking was also employed.

After the interview, the researchers immediately transcribed the conversation and translated it into English. They gave the respondent a copy of the transcript so he could check its trustworthiness. Then, the researchers proceeded to the data analysis using a thematic analysis method. Out of the themes they extracted, they crafted the results and discussion and construct implications of the study. Finally, the final output of the study was presented to the faculty of the Department of Criminal Justice Education of UM Bansalan College.

Ethical Considerations

In this study's conduct, ethical issues and considerations were dealt with mainly before the data was gathered. The researcher underwent an evaluation conducted by the ethics review committee panel members.

Voluntary Participation. The respondents' participation is entirely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy. Information is given whenever the respondents do not understand it before deciding whether to participate in the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality. The records of this study were confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information obtained with this study remained confidential except if necessary to protect the respondents' rights or welfare. The researcher can resist releasing information about their participation to people not connected with the study. When the study results are published or discussed at a conference, no identifiable information will be used. Thus, this research would adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which protects the participants from unauthorized processing of their private or identifiable information or guarantees that their response cannot be traced back to its authentic sources to protect their identity.

Further, the respondents' names did not appear anywhere, and no one except the researcher knew about the respondents' specific answers. If confidential, the researcher assigns a number to the responses, and only the researcher has the key to indicate which number belongs to which respondent. To protect the study participants' rights, all the information gathered from this study is kept private and confidential.

Informed Consent Process. Informed consent was secured from all the respondents to be involved in the study. The researcher gave the respondents a detailed and comprehensive explanation of the purpose of the study. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent should be a voluntary choice. The respondents must have sufficient information and an adequate understanding of the proposed research and the implications of their participation in the study so that the administrators can utilize the results for whatever purpose this may serve them best. The most important thing to consider is that the form must bear the respondent's signature, which implies that he/she participates in the study voluntarily. Moreover, the respondents' personal and private information required in the study was treated with utmost care and kept strictly confidential per RA 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which ensures that all personal data shared shall be safeguarded and protected.

Recruitment. In complying with this ethical policy, the researcher ensured the appropriateness of identified recruiting parties and reviewed the level of risks and measures to mitigate these risks (including physical, psychological, and socioeconomic). The possible discomforts that the respondents may encounter during the survey will be managed by the recruiting parties, especially the researcher.

Risks. This research did not involve high-risk situations that the population may experience regarding physical, psychological, or socioeconomic concerns. It protected and secured the rights of the individuals in the study.

Benefits. This research study is deemed significant to the police officers as they can understand their role as agents of spiritual transformation and moral recovery among offenders. Also, police stations and jail facilities can benefit from this study as they can craft possible interventions that would improve offenders' moral and spiritual well-being. Additionally, this is significant to the religious groups as they can strengthen their spiritual programs for the spiritual and moral betterment of the offenders. Moreover, through the findings, the local government units can devise governmental assistance that can contribute to the recovery and rehabilitation of the offenders. Finally, this study can help future researchers as they can use the results of this study as a reference for their research endeavors.

Safety. Moreover, the safety of the respondents was ensured by using pseudonyms throughout the research to protect their identities. Also, the data gathered from the survey was kept confidential and utilized to verify the study's findings.

Plagiarism. To avoid plagiarism, the researcher underwent the turn-it-in software to ensure that there was no trace/evidence of misrepresentation of someone else's work as his own. The researcher ensured that the correct and accurate way of citing ideas from other writers and scholars was fully observed. To be able to do this, this paper underwent grammar and plagiarism checking via Grammarly and Turnitin software. As this study is based on several existing studies, the researcher ensured they did not make any tales from her literature. Thus, all the information presented is to be carefully written and cited. All sources used in this study came from reliable journals and other scholarly works. This research complied with the citation rules set forth by APA 7th edition citation format; hence, there was no misrepresentation of work or alterations of any data gathered in the study.

Fabrication. The data and information obtained are presented in the most accurate way of writing. Hence, there is no making up of data and results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate. No inconsistency with the existing literature among the information was included in the manuscript.

Falsification. Similarly, falsification was also considered in which there was no trace of purposefully misrepresenting the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation. No evidence of over-claiming or exaggerations.

Conflict of Interest. There is no conflict of interest in this study.

Deceit. The writings in this paper did not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm the respondents' welfare. All the information to be written was checked and validated by the panel of experts. Moreover, deceit was also avoided, which is evidence that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweighs any potential harm to them.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher ensured permission from the municipal police station. The researcher expressed getting written permission from the organization in which the research was undertaken or the location in which the data was collected. Also, the survey questionnaire utilized in this study is clear and comprehensible; the researcher ensured that the participant was fully aware of the benefits the station may get from the study through informed consent. Thus, the survey was conducted with the approval of the concerned authorities as well as the permission of the participant himself.

Authorship. This study considered authorship qualifications for the study's conduct. The researcher, together contributed to the conception and design, acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data. The researcher and adviser collaboratively drafted and revised the article critically for important intellectual content. Both contributed to the study, which led to the publication of the research

Results and Discussion

This section presents the responses of the police-evangelist participant on his motivational factors, experiences, and insights about his role towards moral recovery among offenders. His reactions to the research questions clearly show his narratives on being a police evangelist. Their meaningful utterances are illustrated in italics to provide the readers with the sense that they are talking directly to the respective participants of the study.

Motivational Factors that Influence the Police Evangelist Case to Promote Moral Recovery among Offenders

Table 1. *Themes and core ideas on the motivational factors that influence the police evangelist case to promote moral recovery among offenders*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Driven by Faith and Compassion	The police evangelist is motivated by faith, believing individuals in jail, not inherently "naughty," can change. Recognizing that humans can make mistakes, the evangelist is motivated by compassion for offenders who have wronged. Fueled by faith, the evangelist optimistically believes in the transformative potential of individuals in the criminal justice system.
Responding to the Call	The police evangelist feels responsible for preaching God's Words in jail, providing hope to PDLs, and motivating moral recovery. The evangelist highlights the transformative effect, noting PDLs' happiness upon hearing the Word of God, emphasizing the motivational role of spiritual guidance in moral recovery. The police evangelist sees moral recovery as a divine calling, stressing that not everyone can become a pastor, and those in this position must fulfill God's directive. Emphasizing duty, the evangelist asserts that individuals in the role must adhere to God's instructions in promoting moral recovery.
PDL's Eagerness to be Taught	The police evangelist seizes chances to preach inside, recognizing PDLs' curiosity when they see the Bible, aligning with the divine liking to teach God's Words.

Using within-case thematic analysis, the researchers extracted three (3) emerging themes from the responses of the participants resented in Table 1, which include driven by faith and compassion, responding to the call, and PDL's eagerness to be taught.

Driven by Faith and Compassion. In examining the motivational factors influencing the police evangelist's dedication to promoting moral recovery among offenders, a prominent theme that emerges is "Driven by Faith and Compassion." The police evangelists believe that individuals incarcerated are not inherently "naughty" but rather individuals who have made mistakes. Central to his motivation is the belief that these individuals possess the capacity for positive transformation. Rooted in a sense of duty, the police evangelist sees it as his responsibility to actively facilitate moral recovery, utilizing the influential power of his faith.

In support, Irawan et al. (2022) stated that faithfulness is often a virtue sustaining a service mission. In the context of a police evangelist, this virtue is exemplified through his commitment to sharing the Word of God with PDLs. The police evangelist's faith and compassion serve as a driving force, providing a steadfast foundation for their mission of moral recovery among offenders. This faithfulness is evident in his persistent efforts to bring hope and preach the words of God, even within the challenging environment of a correctional facility.

"Unang una, kining akong pagtuo, ug nagtuo ko nga kining mga nasulod, nasulod ni sila dili tungod kay mga badlungon ni. Naa lang gyuy mga panahon nga makahimo silag mga sala mao nang isa sa mga motivation nako ang akoa gyung pagtuo nga mabag-o sila." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

My first motivation is my faith. Moreover, I believe these persons inside the jail were detained not because they were naughty. Sometimes, they make mistakes, so my motivation is my faith that they will change.

They were responding to the Call. In exploring the motivational factors driving the police evangelist's endeavors of moral recovery among offenders, the theme "Responding to the Call" emerges. The police evangelist, driven by a deep sense of duty to the living God, sees it as imperative to bring hope and preach the words of God even within jail settings. He recognizes the prevailing hopelessness among PDLs and emphasizes the transformative power of faith, believing that through the ministry, individuals can find happiness and hope by engaging with the Word of God.

In connection, this idea supports the claims of Rinawaty and Hannash (2019) that missionaries, pastors, and evangelists are called to convey the truth of the Word of God through sermons, Bible study, and living testimonies that glorify God. When applied to the concept of a police evangelist, it relates to his specific calling to share the Word of God within the context of a correctional facility. Much like missionaries and pastors, the police evangelist responds to a divine calling, recognizing a mission to help PDLs redeem morality through preaching the Word of God. By delivering sermons, engaging in Bible studies, and living out the principles they advocate, the police evangelist becomes a conduit for spiritual guidance and moral recovery.

"Isip ministro sa atong buhi nga Diyos, amoang responsibilidad nga iwali ang pulong sa ginoo bisan pa diha sulod sa prisohan tungod kay daghan ang nagtuo labi na sa atong mga PUPC kay nagtuo sila nga wala na silay paglaum pero sa dihang nakasulod sila, nalipay sila kay nakadungog sila sa pulong sa atong buhi nga diyos." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

As a ministry to our living God, it is our responsibility to preach His Words even in jail because many think, especially the PDLs, that they do not have hope. However, when they were detained, they were happy because they heard the Word of God.

"Dili mn tanan mahimong pastor, so maingon nako nga ang kaning tahas nga gitahas sa atong buhi nga diyos, usa ni ka calling tungod kay dili tanan anaa niini. So kung naa na nga posisyon, khanglan atong buhaton kung unsa ang gustong ipabuhat sa ginoo diri sa atong kinabuhi." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Not all can become a pastor. So, I would say that this task that God asked us to do is a calling because not everyone has this task. So, if you are in this position, you must do what God asked you to do.

PDL's Eagerness to be Taught. Another motivational factor driving the police evangelist's mission to promote moral recovery among offenders is "PDL's Eagerness to be Taught." Recognizing PDLs' eagerness and interest in observing the evangelist reading the Bible, the police evangelist perceives a divine opportunity to fulfill the Lord's desire to teach His words. Despite not being an official duty, the evangelist goes beyond conventional responsibilities, conducting religious services within the correctional facility.

In line with this, Ross (2021) argues that PDLs are often eager to learn the teachings of God due to the transformative power of religion in prison settings. This means that the PDLs' eagerness and receptiveness create a unique opportunity for the police evangelist to contribute to their moral recovery journey. This reciprocal eagerness, where PDLs seek spiritual guidance and the police evangelist responds enthusiastically to teach, highlights the potential for positive transformation and the impactful role of religious teachings in the correctional setting.

"Nakita nako ang opportunity diha sa sulod nga mag wali tungog kay adunay mga panahon nga ang mga PUPC mismo ang nagapangutana mahitungod sa puling sa ginoo. Tungod kay Makita nila nga nagadala kog bibliya, nagatuon ko, hilabi na diha sap ag study sa akoang table. So Makita nila ug nagapakita sila ug interest so akoang gi grab ang opportunity kay usa pud sa kabubut-on sa ginoo nga mapalapngag iyang mga pulong." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

I found an opportunity to preach the Word of God inside because there are times when the PDLs are curious. They usually see me bringing and reading the Bible, especially at my table. They show interest, so I grabbed the opportunity because it is also the liking of the Lord to teach his Words.

“Una man gd, dili mn gd ingon nga nagahimo mi ug service sa sulod. Mao nang kung naay time makagawas, akoa silang gina bible study pero ngadto sa ngadto, ang bible study, gusto gyud nila maexperience ang pagsimba. So sa dihang gusto na nila ma experience ang simba, nag seek ko ug permission sa hepe kung maka service ba ko sa sulod.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

It is not part of our duty to conduct service inside. So I just bible study them when there is a spare time. However, the PDLs wanted to experience the service apart from bible study. So, I sought permission from the chief to conduct service inside.

Experiences of the Police Evangelist Case in His Journey towards Moral Recovery among Offenders

Table 2. Themes and core ideas on the experiences of the police evangelist case in his journey towards moral recovery among offenders

Emerging Themes	Core Ideas
Conduct of Spiritual Services	<p>Outside of official duties, the police evangelist initiates Bible studies during spare time.</p> <p>The evangelist seeks permission to conduct worship services in response to PDLs' eagerness to hear the word of God.</p>
Getting Support	<p>The police evangelist emphasizes unwavering support from family, providing encouragement and motivation during fatigue.</p> <p>Acknowledging churchmates' assistance, the evangelist highlights the role of the church community in fostering resilience on the journey towards moral recovery among offenders.</p> <p>The police evangelist emphasizes the church's significant financial contribution, with some members accompanying him inside, showcasing tangible support for the moral recovery journey.</p> <p>The evangelist notes valuable financial support from churchmates, both those who accompany him and those who do not.</p>
Joy in Changing One's Life	<p>The police evangelist expresses happiness, attributing it to the belief that the Words of God are alive and have the power to change lives.</p> <p>A former PDL now serves the Lord after living with the evangelist's family, validating the positive outcomes of efforts toward moral recovery.</p> <p>The evangelist finds joy in the meaningful results of hard work with God, emphasizing the absence of wasted efforts in the journey to change lives among offenders.</p>
Happiness and Fulfillment	<p>The police evangelist highlights the importance of being happy and spiritually guided in sharing the Words of God, finding fulfillment in meaningful work with God's intervention.</p> <p>Emphasizing that personal fulfillment comes from both happiness in the work and divine assistance; the evangelist underscores God's role in providing happiness and satisfaction in the journey toward moral recovery among offenders.</p> <p>The police evangelist dismisses tiredness, asserting that love for the work and divine assistance transform exhaustion into happiness in the journey toward moral recovery.</p> <p>Despite acknowledging imperfections, the evangelist prioritizes happiness, expressing a commitment to continue sharing the Word of God with joy in the moral recovery journey.</p>
Dealing with PDL's Different Emotions	<p>The police evangelist notes PDLs' varied emotions, ranging from realization and happiness to sadness due to mistakes or false accusations, highlighting the diversity of emotional experiences in the journey toward moral recovery.</p> <p>Amidst PDLs' mixed feelings, the evangelist underscores God's comforting presence, emphasizing spirituality as a support for individuals navigating complex emotions during moral recovery.</p> <p>During service, PDLs openly share not only legal problems but also personal issues.</p> <p>The evangelist identifies family longing as a prevalent issue among PDLs during incarceration, emphasizing the emotional complexities in the moral recovery journey.</p>

Using within-case thematic analysis, the researchers were able to extract four (4) emerging themes from the responses of the participants resented in Table 2, which include the conduct of spiritual services, getting support, joy in changing one's life, happiness and fulfillment, and dealing with PDL's different emotions.

Conduct of Spiritual Services. In exploring the experiences of the police evangelists in their journey toward moral recovery among offenders, a significant theme emerges regarding the conduct of spiritual services. The core ideas underscore the proactive approach of the police evangelist in initiating Bible studies during spare time. He also responds to PDLs' desires to hear God's Words by seeking permission from the police chief to conduct worship services. These actions demonstrate the evangelist's adaptability to the needs of the incarcerated individuals, going beyond official duties to provide spiritual guidance and support.

Connectedly, spirituality and religiousness can provide a framework for recovery, promote hope and personal meaning, and serve as a coping mechanism for detainees inside jail facilities (Glorney et al., 2019). In this context, the spiritual services led by the police evangelist provide a framework for recovery by offering guidance and moral support rooted in religious teachings. By engaging in these activities, detainees are offered hope for redemption and personal meaning, finding solace and direction amidst the challenges of incarceration. Moreover, participation in spiritual services can serve as a coping mechanism, allowing individuals to navigate their circumstances with a sense of purpose and connection to something greater than themselves.

“Una man gd, dili mn gd ingon nga nagahimo mi ug service sa sulod. Mao nang kung naay time makagawas, akoa silang gina bible study pero ngadto sa ngadto, ang bible study, gusto gyud nila maexperience ang pagsimba. So sa dihang gusto na nila ma experience ang simba, nag seek ko ug permission sa hepe kung maka service ba ko sa sulod.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

It is not part of our duty to conduct service inside. So I just bible study them when there is a spare time. However, the PDLs wanted to experience the service apart from bible study. So, I sought permission from the chief to conduct service inside.

They are getting Support. In exploring the police evangelist's experiences in promoting moral recovery among offenders, the theme of "Getting Support" emerges. The core ideas from the responses highlight the support from the evangelist's family and church community. Despite feeling tired sometimes, consistent encouragement from loved ones and churchmates is a strong motivator for the evangelist to continue his mission. Financially, the church provides significant support, with some members even joining the evangelist inside the correctional facility. The collective support, both in presence and financial contributions, underscores a shared commitment from the church community.

Heilat and Seifert (2019) claim that emotional and moral support involves expressing care and compassion during distress, addressing core aspects of one's self. This form of support plays a critical role in relieving distress and augmenting an individual's motivation. Applied to the context of the police evangelist, the emotional, moral, and financial support received from his family and churchmates becomes significant. This support system acts as a source of care and compassion, addressing the core aspects of the police evangelist's well-being. The emotional backing contributes to the relief of distress, and the combined support, including moral and financial elements, augments the evangelist's motivation. This heightened motivation, in turn, propels the police evangelist to engage more actively in spiritual interventions within the jail setting.

“Ang pamilya, naa gyud na kanunay magpalikod sa imong hearts desire. Adunay panahon nga makabati tag kakapoy pero ang pamilya gyud, usa gyud na sila sa mga mag advise sa imoha nga padayon lang, padayon lang, ug ang mga churchmates.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Your family always backs you up with your heart's desire. Sometimes, we will feel tired, but family will always advise us to continue—and, of course, my churchmates.

“Ang church gyud ang usa sa dakog tabang in terms sa fund. Naa koy mga kaubanan nga nagakuyog pud didto. Pero bisan pa pud ug sa mga kaubanan nga wala nagakuyog, nagahatag gihapon sila.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

The church is one of the significant contributors to the fund. Some of my churchmates even accompanied me inside. However, even to my churchmates who do not accompany me, they still contribute funds.

Joy in Changing One's Life. Another theme in the experiences of the police evangelist's journey toward moral recovery among offenders is "Changing One's Life." Grounded in the belief that the Words of God possess dynamic and transformative power, the police evangelist helps change lives within the correctional setting. This means that the spiritual mission has an impact on the moral recovery of individuals. Furthermore, the police evangelist also shared an anecdote about a former PDL who now resides with the police evangelist and actively serves the Lord. This brings happiness to the evangelist and affirms his belief in the positive transformations that result from their collaborative efforts with God.

This is in connection to the findings of Stoorvogel et al. (2019) that the connection between the message of the sermon and the actual question, the listener's challenge, or field of interest are critical factors in a sermon to elicit change. In the context of a police evangelist, this idea relates to observing the positive change in the behavior and disposition of PDLs after engaging in spiritual activities. The effectiveness of the evangelist's message lies in its connection to the specific challenges, questions, and interests of the listeners within the correctional setting. By addressing the unique needs and concerns of the PDLs, the police evangelist creates a meaningful connection, making the spiritual teachings more impactful and transformative.

“Shempre, malipay ta. Tungod kay atoa gyung masinati nga buhi gyud ang puling sa ginoo. Nagabag-o mn gd ni siyag kinabuhi.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Of course, we feel happy because we can say that the Words of God are alive. It changes lives.

"Naa mn tay PUPC nga gikan sa sulod, nya pag gawas niya, sa akua siya nipuyo. Nya karon, kauban na namo siya nga nangalagad sa ginoo. Kana nga mga panghitabo, nagahatag kana siya sa akua ug kalipay. Nakita nako nga sa akoang pag paningkamot sa sulod uban sa ginoo, naay bunga ba. Kumbaga, wala na sayang." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

There was once a PDL here, and when he got out, he lived with us in our home. Now, he is with us in serving the Lord. This event gives me happiness. I see that my hard work with God results in positive things. There is no waste.

Happiness and Fulfillment. This theme emerges because of the evangelist's emphasis on personal happiness and the role of spiritual intervention in sharing the Words of God during the interview. He stresses that true fulfillment in his mission comes not from personal motives but from genuine joy, underlined by the belief that only with God's presence can authentic fulfillment be achieved in his endeavors for moral recovery among offenders. Despite occasional fatigue, the evangelist finds sustained happiness and energy in his mission. Thus, he does not manifest weariness because of the combination of love for his work and divine assistance from God.

Preachers often experience happiness and fulfillment when they preach due to the text's emotional appeal, the preaching approach, and the teaching's positive impact (Kruger & de Klerk, 2021; Pembroke, 2019; Kim, 2021). The idea that the police evangelist feels happiness and fulfillment when preaching, despite occasional tiredness, can be related to the belief that God has blessed them with preaching skills. The emotional appeal of the text, combined with the theocentric approach focusing on God as the center of therapeutic preaching, aligns with the evangelist's belief that his skills are a divine gift. Moreover, despite moments of fatigue, the positive impact of their teaching on the lives of PDLs contributes to an enduring sense of happiness and fulfillment.

"dili ka pwede mag share sa pulong kung wala kay kalipay sa imong ginabuhay, kung wala kay spiritual interventions sa pag share. SO importante gyud nga pangayoon nimo iyang giya kung mao ba ni imong misyon. Kung sa imong kaugalingon lang, siguro at first, makabati kag kalipay pero di gyud ka makabati ug fulfillment kay ang ginoo ram n jud ang makahatag nimo ana. So mabati nato na tungod kay atom n pong gikalipay nya naa poy tabang gikan sa diyos." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

You cannot share the Words of God if you are not happy with what you are doing and do not have the intervention of the spiritual force upon sharing. So, it is essential to ask for His guidance. If you do it alone, you cannot feel fulfilled because only God can give you that. We can only feel fulfilled because we are happy with what we do, and God is there to help us.

"Ang kakapoy naa ra na sa huna huna pero kung gusto nimo imong ginabuhay nya naa poy tabang sa diyos, dili gyud ka makabati ug kakapoy, instead imoha nang ikalipay. Pero bisan kita dili ta hanas sa pag share sa pulong sa ginoo, ni share ta kay gusto ug malipay mn ta nga mo sgare sa uban." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Tiredness is only in the min. However, if you love what you are doing and God helps you, you can never be tired. You will be happy instead. Even if we are not excellent at sharing the Word of God, we still do it anyway because we are happily sharing it with others.

They are dealing with Different Emotions. In delving into the experiences of the police evangelist's journey towards moral recovery among offenders, "Dealing with Different Emotions" emerges. The core ideas of the responses reveal the diverse emotional landscape of PDLs within the correctional facility, ranging from remorse and joy to profound realizations. Some PDLs find solace in God's goodness, while others derive happiness and a sense of purpose through encountering the Words of God. The police evangelist emphasizes the crucial role of faith in providing comfort amid these varied emotions in the correctional environment. Moreover, during the services, PDLs openly share legal issues and personal problems, with a prevalent concern being the profound longing for their families. The evangelist underscores the multifaceted challenges PDLs face beyond legal matters, shedding light on the emotional strain caused by separation from their families within the jail setting.

According to Labuschagne and Steenkamp (2023), pastors often deal with a range of emotions from their constituents when counseling or preaching, which can significantly impact their own emotional well-being and performance. In connection to this, there is also a complex emotional landscape within the correctional as the police evangelist has dealt with a range of emotions from PDLs, such as anger, sadness, longing, happiness, and realizations. Despite encountering these diverse emotions, the police evangelist remains steadfast in his mission to teach the Word of God. This resilience speaks to his commitment and determination to provide spiritual guidance, even in challenging emotional dynamics. This further means that managing a spectrum of emotions is an inherent aspect of being a police evangelist, and the ability to remain focused on the mission contributes to the effectiveness of fostering moral recovery among PDLs.

"Didto sa sulod, ang uban naay mohilak, siguro mabati nila nga mayo gihapon ang ginoo despite sa ilang mga nabuhay nga sala. Aduna puy uban malipay tungod kay abi nila ang prisoan, basurahan, ngit ngit. Pero sa dihang na preso sila, nakabati na hinuon sila sa pulong sa ginoo. Siguro ang uban nag huna huna sila nga ang nahitabo sa ilang kinabuhi kay pagpukaw ba nga basig nakalimtan na nila ang ginoo. Naa poy masubo kay damdamon gyud kay dili mn ingon an aka dako ilang salaod or wala gyuy sala. Mixed feelings gyud pero aduna mn ang pulong sa ginoo nga naga comfort sa ilaha." (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Some PDLs cry because they realize that God is still good to them despite their wrongdoings. Some also feel happy because they think that jails are trash and gloomy, but when they get in, they can hear God's Words instead. Some also believe that the misfortunes they experience are just a wake-up call to return to God. Some are sad because they dwell hard on their mistakes or are just wrongfully accused of crimes they did not do. There are mixed feelings, but God is there to comfort them.

“During service, naay panahon nga mo vouce out sila mahitungod sa ilang mga problema. Gawas sa ilang mga giatubang nga kaso, naa poy ubang mga problema nga ilang gina voice out. Shempre kung naa ka sa sulod, an kamingaw sa pamilya, usa gyid na sa problema didto sa sulod.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

During service, they will voice out their problems. Apart from their cases, they share other issues. Of course, if they are inside the jail, the longing for their family is an emergent problem.

Insights of the Police Evangelist Case about the Jobs of Police Officers towards Moral Recovery among Offenders

Using within-case thematic analysis, the researchers extracted three (3) emerging themes from the participants' responses resented in Table 3, which include volunteerism in sharing God's words, God's words change Lives, and do what you learned.

Table 3. *Themes and core ideas on the insights of the police evangelist case about the jobs of police officers towards moral recovery among offenders*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Volunteerism in Sharing God's Words	The police evangelist emphasizes free and voluntary sharing of the Word of God, rejecting any payment to maintain a sense of volunteerism. Firmly refusing monetary compensation, the evangelist expresses concern about hindering divine compensation, reinforcing the commitment to volunteerism. The police evangelist expects future reward from God for their voluntary efforts in sharing the Word, highlighting a perspective focused on divine compensation in the journey of moral recovery.
God's Words Change Lives	The police evangelist emphasizes the transformative power of sharing God's Words to instill hope and positive change, recognizing its potential impact on realizing wrongfulness. Citing instances of positive change, the evangelist underscores the importance of willingness to learn, leading to newfound hope and showcasing the transformative impact of spiritual guidance. The police evangelist firmly believes in the sufficiency of God's Words for changing lives, expressing confidence in the comprehensive impact of spiritual teachings on individuals seeking positive transformation.
Do What You Learned; Do What You Commit	The police evangelist urges officers to listen and actively apply their learning for moral recovery. Achieving moral recovery involves wholehearted listening and obedience to the Lord's will, emphasizing commitment to spiritual principles. The evangelist stresses that moral recovery comes from applying learned lessons, emphasizing the importance of active implementation over passive listening.

Volunteerism in Sharing God's Words. In exploring the insights of the police evangelist regarding the roles of police officers in moral recovery among offenders, the theme "Volunteerism in Sharing God's Words" emerges. The core ideas from the responses center on the police evangelist's firm belief that sharing the Word of God is a voluntary and unpaid service, rejecting any form of payment. The evangelist sees their service as an investment in receiving God's compensation in the future, emphasizing the spiritual fulfillment derived from volunteering.

Volunteering is perceived as a means for individuals to connect with the divine by embodying the desire to give, fostering unity with those in need, and becoming integrated with the heavenly world (Nistor, 2022). About this, the idea that the police evangelist is undertaking his mission to share the words of God with PDLs for free, driven by the belief in a greater reward in the afterlife, aligns with this perception of volunteering. The evangelist embodies the desire to give in a material sense and by sharing spiritual guidance. This act fosters unity with those in need, specifically the PDLs, and integrates the police evangelist with the divine world through their selfless service.

“Ang pag share sa pulong sa ginoo, wala nay bayad. Nadawat nato na nga libre, atong eshare sa uban ga libre. So bisan piso, wala tay bayad. Kining atoa, boluntaryo. Nahadlok ko kay kung magpabayad ta karon, basig wala na tay suhol madawat gikan saatong buhi nga diyos. So kining atong gibuhat karon, ang suhol ani, unya na inig balik sa diyos.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Sharing the Word of God is free. We received it complimentary, so we gave it away for free. We do not accept pay for even a single peso. We are volunteers. If we ask for pay, we will not receive God's compensation. So, this thing we are doing now will be paid for when God finally returns.

God's Words Change Lives. The police evangelist's responses to his insights highlight the transformative impact of spiritual guidance, emphasizing the theme "God's Words Change Lives." He stresses the significance of sharing the Words of God with individuals, particularly those with low morale due to criminal activities. The evangelist believes in the power of God's Words to help individuals recognize the wrongfulness of their actions and find hope for positive change. Instances of positive transformation are cited, underscoring the importance of willingness to learn. The evangelist contends that God's Words can change lives and facilitate recovery

from hopelessness.

Booker (2018) explores the transformative influence of God's spirit on an African American Christian minister, indicating that the words and actions of God can profoundly affect individuals. In connection to this, the idea that the police evangelist believes in the power of God's Words to help individuals recognize the wrongfulness of their actions and find hope for positive change aligns with the transformative influence explored by Booker. The police evangelist perceives the Words of God as a powerful force that influences individuals profoundly, prompting self-reflection and fostering a sense of hope and positive change. This connection emphasizes the belief in the transformative power of divine teachings, reinforcing the police evangelist's conviction in the efficacy of spiritual guidance as a catalyst for moral recovery among those within the correctional setting.

“Ang pagtabang sa mga less fortunate or PDL, importante kaayo tungod kay nagkinahanglan na sila spiritual advise ug word of god. Low morale na mn gd na sila tungod sa ilang nabuhat nga krimen. Nagdahom na sila nga wala na silay paglaum. Tungod sa puling sa ginoo nga ilang nadungug, ang ilang kinabuhi nga naa sa kadaot, siguro naman naay kaubasan nya ilang ma realize nga ilang gibuhay kay dili mayo. Kung dili mn tanan, naa gyuy uban diha nga inig gawas, naa gyuy kabag-ohan. So tungod na sa pulong sa ginoo.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

Helping the less fortunate or PDLs is very important because they need spiritual advice and the words of God. They have low morale because of their crime, so they think they do not have hope. Because of the Words of God, their damaged life will be transformed since they will realize what they did was wrong.

“Daghan ang mga proweba nga tungod sa pulong sa ginoo, ang mga tao nausab. Kung aduna silay willingness sa pagtuon, mamahimo silang hopeful ug malaumon kung ilaha gyung tun-an ug ikinabuhi ang pulong sa ginoo.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

There is much proof that because of the Word of God, people change. If they are willing to learn, they will become hopeful.

“Ang pulong sa ginoo, sakto na gyud ni, haom na ni aron sap ag usab sa kinabuhi sa tao aron maka recover sila sa ilang nawala nga pag laum. Sakto na ang pulong sa diyos kay naan a diha tanan.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

God's Words are enough to change a person's life and to make him recover from hopelessness. The words of God are enough because everything you need is in there.

Do What You Learned; Do What You Commit. This theme emphasizes the critical importance of action in conjunction with listening, meaning that individuals pursuing moral recovery should not merely hear but also wholeheartedly obey the will of the Lord. The evangelist stresses the active role of applying spiritual teachings, emphasizing that proper moral recovery is achieved through the practical application of these lessons.

In connection, Murti (2021) argues that experiential learning is an effective method in the classroom environment to teach the learner what has to be learned. The idea that the active role of applying spiritual teachings is crucial, emphasizing that proper moral recovery is achieved through the practical application of these lessons, aligns with the principles of experiential learning. Just as experiential learning involves actively engaging with the subject, applying spiritual teachings in real-life situations becomes a transformative and integral part of the learning process. The emphasis on practical application ensures a more profound internalization of moral principles, mirroring the effectiveness of experiential learning in instilling lasting lessons.

“Sa akoang ginaingon, dili lang sila kutob sa paminaw dapat, ilaha pud dapat buhaton. Aron ma acheve nila ang moral recovery, dapat kinasang-kasing ilang pagpaminaw sa pulong sa diyos nya kinahananglan ilang buhaton nya ilang tumanon ang kabubut-on sa buhi nga diyos.” (P1 – Jaysonel Boy)

As I have said, they should not only listen; they should do what they learned. To achieve moral recovery, they should wholeheartedly listen and obey the will of the Lord.

Conclusion

The study has explored what drives a police evangelist in his mission for moral recovery among offenders. He is motivated by his strong faith, a sense of response to the calling, and the genuine eagerness of PDLs to learn. His experiences unfold with the support of family and friends, witnessing positive changes in inmates, finding personal joy and fulfillment, and journeying the ups and downs of emotions in the incarcerated community.

Moreover, the police evangelist also expressed insights reflecting on his journey towards the moral recovery of the PDLs. This involves the idea that the mix of faith and community support is essential in helping PDLs in their moral recovery. The happiness and fulfillment expressed by the police evangelist highlight the impact of volunteering with a real sense of mission on one's life. Positive transformations in PDLs reinforce the idea that sharing spiritual teachings can make a difference in the criminal justice setting.

On a personal note, what emerges in this paper is the importance of utmost commitment to moral recovery. This study highlights that actively getting involved and genuinely caring is critical to making a positive impact. The police evangelist's insights drive home the point that spreading God's words is not just a kind gesture but a catalyst for fundamental, positive changes in the lives of offenders.

Ultimately, our research paints a picture of hope and guidance for those lending a hand and those seeking a fresh start within the criminal justice system.

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